

Prevalence of Malaria Parasitemia among Pregnant Women Attending Ante-Natal Clinic at Bingham University Teaching Hospital Plateau State

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ABSTRACT

In this study a prevalence of 29.1% malaria parasitemia among pregnant women attending Bingham University Teaching Hospital (BUTH) was recorded. The study also showed that multigravidae had the highest prevalence of malaria parasitemia 18.8%, followed by primigravidae who had the lowest prevalence of 10.3%. The age group of 26 to 30 years had the highest prevalence of 11.5% followed by the age group of 31 to 35 years (8.5%) while the least prevalence of 0.6% was in the age group of 41 to 45 years. Women in their first trimester had 2.4% prevalence followed by women in their second trimester who had the prevalence of 12.1% and those in their third trimester had the prevalence rate of 14.9%. The study also shows the result of pregnant women who use long-lasting insecticide treated nets had the highest prevalence of 17.0% while those who do not use the long-lasting insecticide treated nets had the lowest prevalence of 12.1%. At the end of the study the result showed the prevalence rate of 29.1% of malaria parasitemia. Pregnancy is among other factors affecting the prevalence of malaria in pregnant women which is due to low immunity during pregnancy.

Keywords: Malaria; Parasitemia;
Trimester; Pregnant women;
Multigravidae

INTRODUCTION

Malaria is a parasitic disease that affects the red blood cells. In West Africa, the species of protozoa (*Plasmodium*) known to cause malaria include- *P. falciparum*, *P. vivax*, *P. malariae* and *P. ovale*. The parasite is transmitted by the female mosquito of the *Anopheles* genus (Samak, 2004). Upto 2 billion people are affected by malaria worldwide. About 300-500 million cases are reported annually with 2-3 million deaths per year. Ninety percent of these cases occur in Africa most among pregnant women and children under 5 years of age (WHO, 2000). The exact burden of the disease in Nigeria is difficult to ascertain for many reasons including poor record keeping. Malaria in Pregnancy is a major public health problem in tropical and sub-tropical regions of the World. The physiological changes that occur in pregnancy and the pathological effects of malaria have a synergistic effect on the course of the illness. Malaria in pregnancy tends to be more deadly. All these make the management of malaria in pregnancy more difficult. Even though direct maternal mortality from malaria is less common in areas of stable transmission, *P. falciparum* infection is estimated to cause upto 10,000 maternal deaths annually as well as 8-14% of all low birth weight babies and 3-8% of all infant deaths annually.

Malaria in pregnancy has serious consequences to the mother and her unborn baby. Pregnant women in endemic areas are vulnerable to malaria because pregnancy reduces a woman's immunity to malaria making her susceptible to infection than non-pregnant women and increasing the risk of anaemia. The evidence of malaria infection can be obtained from the detection of malaria parasites in the peripheral blood of pregnant women (Brabin,1991).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

This study was carried out in Bingham University Teaching Hospital (BUTH), Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria. Jos Plateau State where the Hospital is located got its name from its unique geographical features. The free encyclopedia (Wikipedia) states that Jos is a city in Nigeria's middle belt located at 9^o56'N, 8^o53'E, 9.933^oN, 8.883^oE high on the Jos Plateau, with an altitude of 4,062 feet (1.217m) above sea level. It enjoys a more temperate climate than most of the rest of Nigeria (average monthly temperature ranges from 70^oF – 77^oF or 21^oC – 25^oC and has a mean temperature of 18.7^oC maximum at 51.7^oC).

Study population

The study was carried out on pregnant women attending ante-natal clinic at Bingham University Teaching Hospital

(BUTH), Jos, between the period of November 2015 to January 2016.

Inclusion criteria

Pregnant women attending ante-natal clinic at Bingham University Teaching Hospital Jos, (BUTH) were eligible to be recruited for the study.

Exclusion criteria

Non pregnant women attending Bingham University Teaching Hospital (BUTH), Jos.

Ethical considerations

The ethical approval was sought and obtained from the ethical committee of Bingham University Teaching Hospital, (BUTH) prior to the commencement of the study.

Patient informed consent

Patient's consent and approval were sought prior to sample collection. Participation was voluntary and those who gave their consent were enrolled in the study.

Determination of sample size

The sample size for this study was determined using the formula described by Thrusfield (1997) as shown below:

$$n = \frac{(1.97)^2 P_{exp} (1 - P_{exp})}{d^2}$$

Where: - n = Minimum sample size
p = Expected prevalence of malaria parasitemia in Nigerian pregnant women (12% Singh et al., 2012).

d = Desired absolute precision of 5%

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.11 (1 - 0.11)}{0.05^2}$$

$$= \frac{3.8416 \times 0.11 \times 0.89}{0.0025} = 150.437056$$

A Maximum number of 165 sample size was determined.

Specimen collection

Capillary blood was collected for this study. The patients were made to sit comfortably, the thumb was cleaned with cotton wool soaked in 70% Alcohol and allowed to air dry, a quick prick was made with a disposable sterile blood lancet. The first ooze of blood was wiped off with a

dry cotton wool, a little pressure was applied to the thumb to ensure free flow of the blood, the subsequent drops of blood were placed on a clean grease free slide for thin and thick films and labelled appropriately.

Specimen processing

Thin and thick blood films were made for the study and were stained with Giemsa staining method. The thin and thick blood films were microscopically examined using oil immersion (X100 objective lens) and results recorded appropriately. Controls (positive and negative blood films) were also examined ensuring accuracy of the procedures.

Data analysis

Data were analysed using statistical software (Version 21 SPSS). The analysis was considered to be statistically insignificant where the P-value obtained was >0.05.

RESULTS

Plasmodium falciparum was identified as the causative agent of malaria parasitemia. One hundred and sixty-five blood samples were collected from the pregnant women attending ante-natal clinic at Bingham University Teaching Hospital (BUTH) Jos and analyzed for malaria parasitemia. The result of the study is presented in tables as follows: -

Table 1 shows the prevalence of malaria parasitemia in relation to gravidae. From a total of 54 primigravidae, 17

tested positive with a prevalence of 10.3% while the remaining 111 multigravidae recorded a prevalence of 18.8%.

Table 2 shows the prevalence of malaria parasitemia in relation to the ages of the pregnant women. The highest prevalence of malaria was 11.5% among the 26 to 30 years while the lowest prevalence (0.6%) was seen in the age range of 41 to 45 years.

Table 3 shows the prevalence of malaria parasitemia in relation to trimesters. Malaria parasitemia was most prevalent in the third trimester (14.9%), followed by the second trimester (12.1%) and lastly first trimester (2.4%).

Table 4 shows the prevalence of malaria parasitemia in relation to the use of long-lasting insecticide-treated nets (LLIN). 99 pregnant women who use the long-lasting insecticide-treated nets had a prevalence of (17.0%) and 66 pregnant women who do not use the long-lasting insecticide-treated nets recorded a prevalence of (12.1%).

The overall distribution of *Plasmodium* species of pregnant women in Bingham University Teaching Hospital (BUTH) of Jos North Local Government Area by gravidae, age, trimesters and the use of long-lasting insecticide-treated nets were calculated by Chi-Square test and concluded that there was no significant difference in the malaria parasite infection by gravidae, age, trimesters and the use of long-lasting insecticide-treated nets since 165 pregnant women were examined with 48 positive samples having a prevalence of 29.1%.

Table 1: Prevalence of malaria parasitemia in pregnant women attending ante-natal clinic in BUTH in relation to gravidae

Gravidae	No. examine	No. positive (%)	P-value
Primigravidae	54	17(10.3)	0.637
Multigravidae	111	31(18.8)	
Total	165	48(29.1)	

Table 2: Prevalence of malaria parasitemia in pregnant women attending ante-natal clinic at BUTH in relation to age

Age	No. examine	No. positive (%)	P-value
21-25	21	7(4.2)	0.956
26-30	62	19(11.5)	
31-35	55	14(8.5)	
36-40	23	7(4.2)	
41-45	4	1(0.6)	
Total	165	48(29.1)	

Table 3: Prevalence of malaria parasitemia in pregnant women attending ante-natal clinic at BUTH in relation to trimesters

Trimester	No. Examined	No. Positive	P-value
1 st Trimester	23	4(2.4)	0.840
2 nd Trimester	71	20(12.1)	
3 rd Trimester	71	24(14.9)	
Total	165	48(29.1)	

Table 4: Prevalence of malaria parasitemia in pregnant women attending ante-natal clinic at BUTH in relation to sleeping under long-lasting insecticide treated nets

LLIN	No. Examined	No. Positive	P-value
Use of LLIN	99	28(17.0)	0.840
Not use LLIN	66	20(12.1)	
Total	165	48(29.1)	

DISCUSSION

In this study, a prevalence of 29.1% malaria parasitemia among pregnant women attending Bingham University Teaching Hospital (BUTH) was recorded. This finding is lower compared to the previous report of (Jambo *et al.*, 2011) and (Aribodor *et al.*, 2009) who recorded a prevalence of 42.4% in Makurdi, and 64.4% in Nigeria. The disparity of this study may be due to the fact that the study was conducted during the dry season between the months of November 2015 to January 2016 where mosquitoes are less abundant according to (Ayanda, 2009) in Nasarawa State, Nigeria, prevalence of *Plasmodium falciparum* infection is higher in the wet season than in the dry season. It might also be due to the fact that the subjects were constantly attending their ante-natal clinics where they are given regular health education, long-lasting insecticide-treated nets and intermittent prophylaxis therapy (IPT). However, this report was higher compared with previous findings of (Neeru *et al.*, 2001) in India and (Isah *et al.*, 2012) in Nigeria who reported the prevalence of 1.3% and 3.1% respectively.

The study also showed that multigravidae had the highest prevalence of malaria parasitemia 18.8%, followed by primigravidae who had the lowest prevalence of 10.3%. This result is statistically insignificant $P > 0.05$. (Taura *et al.*, 2009) who recorded the highest prevalence of 45.2% among multigravidae pregnant women attending ante-natal clinic in Sir Mohammed Sanusi Specialist Hospital Kano Nigeria and (Ikeh *et al.*, 2005) who recorded the lowest prevalence of 7.2% among multigravidae pregnant women in Jos University Teaching Hospital Nigeria. This could be as a result that primigravidae are less susceptible to malaria parasite than multigravidae because they have certain level of immunity to malaria parasite before they were pregnant.

The age group of 26 to 30 years had the highest prevalence of 11.5% followed by the age group of 31 to 35 years (8.5%) while the least 0.6% was in the age group of 41 to 45 years. No significant age related but the result was in agreement with the previous findings of (Adefioye *et al.*, 2007) in Ladoko Akintola University of Technology Osogbo, Nigeria who recorded the highest prevalence of 66.3% malaria parasitemia among pregnant women in the age group of 28 to 31 years. (Uko *et al.*, 2010) who recorded a low prevalence rate of 6.8%. The prevalence of malaria decrease with increase in age of the women, reasons might be that younger women are careless in covering themselves compared to the older women and also younger women have low immunity when it comes to pregnancy than the older women who have had multiple birth and exposure to malaria which confirm an increase immunity in young women.

Women in their first trimester had 2.4% prevalence followed by women in their second trimester who had the prevalence of 12.1% and those in their third trimester had the prevalence rate of 14.9%. The result is not statistically significant $P > 0.05$. The result agreed with the previous findings of (Singh *et al.*, 2012) who recorded highest prevalence among women in their third trimester 39.2% reason being that the women in their third trimester have low resistance and immunity to malaria parasite. In contrary is the findings of (Coulibaly *et al.*, 2004) who recorded the lowest prevalence of 4.4% among pregnant women in their third trimester in Burkina Faso. This may be due to the fact that at the onset of pregnancy, natural immunity is active though it gradually reduce as the pregnancy progresses.

The study also shows the result of pregnant women who use long-lasting insecticide treated nets had the highest prevalence of 17.0% while those who do not use the long-lasting insecticide treated nets had the lowest prevalence of 12.1%. The results are statistically insignificant $P > 0.05$. Even though some who uses the long-lasting insecticide treated nets were still positive, reason being that they could be bitten by mosquitoes out door. This result is in agreement with the previous findings of (Nyamngee *et al.*, 2014) who recorded the highest prevalence of 86.2% among pregnant women who use long-lasting insecticide treated nets in Ekiti Nigeria. This is associated with the lack of formal education about the consequences of malaria parasitemia in pregnancy (Augustine *et al.*, 2012) who recorded the lowest prevalence of 7.5% among pregnant women who do not use long-lasting insecticide treated nets in Abuja Nigeria. Reasons may be that these women were on prophylaxis and having high immunity to malaria.

CONCLUSION

At the end of the study the result showed the prevalence rate of 29.1% of malaria parasitemia. Pregnancy is among other factors affecting the prevalence of malaria in pregnant women which is due to low immunity during pregnancy. It is evidence that asymptomatic malaria parasitemia is common among the ante-natal pregnant women. It was properly stated from the study that the third trimester, multigravidae, and the young age are at greater risk of malaria parasitemia.

RECOMMENDATION

Malaria in pregnancy is preventable if the following can be strictly adhered to:

Insecticide treated nets should be given to the pregnant women free of charge on their first visit.

Ante natal care unit should educate the pregnant women on the dangers and effects of malaria and how to prevent being bitten by mosquitoes and also to keep their environments clean.

Anti-malarial drugs should be given to the pregnant women on their first ante natal visit whether they show symptoms or not.

Government should incorporate more special health education directed at pregnant women into their malaria enlightenment campaigns and provide free chemo prophylactic drugs to pregnant women.

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REFERENCES

- Adefioye, O. A., Adeyeba, O.A., Hassan, W.O., and Oyeniran, O.A (2007): Prevalence of malaria parasite infection among pregnant women in Oshogbo, Southwest, Nigeria. *American-Eurasian Journal of Scientific Research.*, 2(1):43-45.
- Aribodor, D.N., Nwaorgu, C.O., Eneanya, C.I., Okoli, I., Worley, R.P., and Etaga, H. O (2009): Association of low birth weight and placental malaria infection in Nigeria. *Journal of Infection in Developing Countries.*, 3(8): 620-623.
- Augustine Ankanahi, Samson B. Adeboye, Ekundayo D. Aragundedel, Jennifer Ayuanti Ernest Nwokolo, Olorenke Ladipo and Martin M. Meremikwu (2012): Antipyretic

measure for testing fever in malaria. *Journal of American Medical Association.* 12:105.

- Ayanda, O (2009): Relative abundance of adult female anopheles' mosquitoes in Uga, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. *Journal of Parasitology and Vector Biology*, 1(1) pp. 005-008.
- Brabin, B.J., (1991): The risk and severity of malaria in pregnant women. In Applied Field Research in Malaria. Report No.1, WHO, pp 1- 34.
- Coulibaly S.O, Desire N, Traore S, Kone B, Magnussen P. (2004): Therapeutic efficiency of sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine and chloroquine for uncomplicated malaria in pregnancy in Burkina Faso. *Malaria Journal* 5:49
- Ikeh, S. N., Akudo V. E., Uguru A. J. (2005): Relationship with birth weight and fetal haemoglobin levels in Nigeria. *Clinical Journal of Microbiology* 6(2):91 – 94.
- Isah A. Y, Amanabo K, Ekele B. A. (2012): Prevalence of malaria parasitemia amongst asymptomatic pregnant women attending a Nigerian Teaching Hospital. *Annal of African Medicine* 10(2):171-4
- Jambo G.T.A., Mbaawuaga E M., Ayegba A. S. Araoye M. A. (2011): Anaemia, malaria burden and its control methods among pregnant women in a semi-urban community of northern Nigeria. *Journal of Public Health and Epidemiology*.3(7): 317-323.
- Samak A.C. (2004): Malaria in Pregnancy: an overview. *McGill* 8(1). 66-71.
- Nyamngee Amae, Edungbola Luke Dayol, Edogun Abike Helen and Akanbi Ajibola Alru, G.J.B.A. H.S. (2014): Malaria parasitemia among pregnant women possessing freely donated insecticide treated net in Ado Ekiti Nigeria. 3(1): 86 – 91.
- Neeru Sign, Mrigendra P. Singh, Blair J. Wylie, Mobalsir Hussan Yeboah A Kojo, Chander Shekhar, Lara Sabin, Meghna Desai, V. Udhayakkumar, and Davidson H. Hammer (2012): Malaria prevalence among pregnant women in two districts with deficiency endemicity in Chhattisgarh India. *African Journal of malaria* 1(1): 27-40.
- Singh N, Shukla M.M, Srivastava R, Sharma V.P. (2012): Prevalence of malaria among pregnant and non-pregnant women of district Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh. *Indian Journal Malaria*. 32:6–13.
- Taura D. W. and Oyeyi T. I. (2009): Prevalence of malaria parasites in pregnant women attending Sunusi Specialist Hospital Kano Bayero. *Journal of Pure and Applied Science* 2(1) :186-188
- Uko, Ek, A.O Emeribe and G.C. Ejejie. (2010): malaria infection of the placenta and neo-natal low birth weight in Calabar. *Journal of Medical Laboratory Science.* 7:7-10.
- World Health Organization (2000): Expert Committee on Malaria. *World Health Organization Technical Report Series*, No 892.pp. I-V.

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